

Developing HPC RSE Capabilities

Overview:

- Where are we?
- What do we want to go?
- How will we get there?

How much do you agree with the following statements?

I have sufficient time for CPD

I know what CPD myself and my team need

I know where to source the CPD

The CPD needed is of sufficient quality

Strongly disagree

Strongly agree

What are your immediate training priorities?

What are upcoming training priorities?

What barriers (if any exist)?

How can we work together as community to improve HPC RSE CPD?

What are our next steps?